

GENERATION OF ANTI-MAGIC PLANAR BIPARTITE GRAPHS FROM PATHS

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Abstract

Hartsfield and Ringel conjectured that every tree other than the tree on two vertices has an anti-magic labeling. In spite of several research papers published, the conjecture remains open. A very few results deal with proving some classes of graphs are anti-magic. In this paper, we identified a new class of anti-magic planar bipartite graphs that are generated from paths.

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1. Introduction

In this paper, we consider finite, undirected and simple graphs. For graph theoretic definitions, refer the text [6]. An anti-magic labeling of a graph G is a 1-1 and on-to function defined on the set of edges of a graph to $\{1, 2, \dots, |E|\}$ such that the vertex labels are defined as the sum of the edge labels of the edges that are incident to it are different. A graph that admits anti-magic labeling is called as anti-magic graphs. Anti-magic labeling of graphs was first studied by Hartsfield and Ringel [3] and they conjectured that every tree other than the tree on two vertices has an anti-magic labeling.

Even though various articles were published on anti-magic graphs, conjectures remain open for more than two decades. To mention a few standard results, Liang and Zhu [5] proved that 3-regular graphs are anti-magic and Kaplan et al [4] proved some trees with some degree

restrictions are anti-magic graphs. For a thorough and deep understanding of the results on anti-magic graphs, refer the dynamic survey by Gallian[2].

2. Main Result

In this section, we will construct a new class of planar bipartite graphs $PLB(n)$. To construct $PLB(n)$, consider a path on n vertices and visualize the path as a bipartite graph (V_1, V_2) . Now, add a new vertex u and make it adjacent to all the vertices of V_1 . Similarly add a new vertex v and make it adjacent to all the vertices of V_2 . Graph thus obtained is a planar graph and as well as a bipartite graph. One can easily observe that $PLB(n)$ has $n + 2$ vertices and $2n-1$ edges. Graphs $PLB(7)$ and $PLB(10)$ are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively.

Note: If n is odd, we call $PLB(n)$ as the unbalanced planar bipartite graph and if n is even, then we call $PLB(n)$ as the balanced planar bipartite graph.

Figure 1: Planar bipartite graph $PLB(7)$

Figure 2: Planar bipartite graph PLB(10)

Theorem 2.1 Unbalanced planar bipartite graphs $PLB(n)$ are anti-magic whenever n is odd.

Proof: Let us consider ϕ as the anti-magic labeling of path on n vertices, where n is odd. Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the set of vertices of P_n such that they were arranged in the increasing order of their weight as defined the anti-magic labeling ϕ . Observe that the partition of vertices is unbalanced as n is odd. To construct the bipartite planar graph from the path, let us introduce two new vertices u and w such that the vertex u is adjacent to one partition of vertices of path and the vertex w is made adjacent to the other partition of vertices of path. Now, the edge set of planar bipartite graph has two disjoint partitions as $E(PLB(n)) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \cup \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$, where e_i 's are the original edges of the path and $w_i = (u, v_i)$ or (w, v_i) as the case may be.

Now, let us define the anti-magic labeling φ for the planar bipartite graph $PLB(n)$ using the anti-magic labeling ϕ .

$$\varphi(e_i) = \phi(e_i), 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$\varphi(w_i) = n + i, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

From the above labeling, it is clear that the edge labels of edges of are defined in the set $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2n-1\}$ and as well no edge label gets repeated. Therefore, ϕ is bijective. Vertex sum of vertices of v_i , for $1 \leq i \leq n$ becomes the sum of vertex sum of vertex v_i as defined by ϕ , n and i . Vertices of $PLB(n)$ can be arranged based on their vertex sum as follows:

$$u, w, v_1 v_2, \dots, v_n$$

Therefore, planar bipartite graph $PLB(n)$ admits anti-magic labeling and thus $PLB(n)$ is an anti-magic graph when n is odd. This completes the proof.

3. Illustrative example

In this section, we illustrate our main result that $PLB(n)$ admits anti-magic labeling whenever n is odd. Figure 3 shows the anti-magic labeling of path on 7 vertices and Figure 4 shows the anti-magic labeling of $PLB(7)$.

Figure 3: Anti-magic labeling of path on 7 vertices

Figure 4: Anti-magic labeling of PLB(7)

4. Conclusion and future directions

In this paper, we identified a new class of planar bipartite graphs to be anti-magic. This new class of planar bipartite graphs has been generated from the path. In this context, our result supports the conjecture that every graph other than the complete graph on 2 vertices are anti-magic.

References

- [1] N. Alon, G. Kaplan, A. Lev, Y. Roditty, R. Yuster, Dense graphs are antimagic, *J. Graph Theory* 47, (2004), 297-309.
- [2] J.A. Gallian, A Dynamic Survey of Graph Labeling, *The Electronic Journal of Combinatorics*, 22nd Edition, (2019), #DS6.
- [3] N. Hartsfield, G. Ringel, *Pearls in Graph Theory*, Academic Press, INC, Boston, 1990, 108-109, Revised version 1994.
- [4] G. Kaplan, A. Lev, Y. Roditty, On zero-sum partitions and anti-magic trees, *Discrete Math.* 309, (2009), 2010-2014.
- [5] Y. Liang, X. Zhu, Anti-magic labeling of cubic graphs, *J. Graph Theory* 75 (2014), 31-36.
- [6] D.B. West, *Introduction to Graph Theory*, Prentice Hall of India, 2nd Edition, 2001.
- [7] Yu-Chang Liang, Tsai-Lien Wong, Xuding Zhu, Anti-magic labeling of trees, *Discrete Math.*,331, (2014), 9-14.
- [8] Y. Hou and W.C. Shiu, The spectrum of the edge corona of two graphs, *Elec. Jour. Of Lin. Alge*, 20 (2010), 586-594.